

Synthesis and characterization by means of IR, ^1H , ^{13}C , ^{119}Sn NMR and FAB-MS spectroscopy of some new organotin(IV) complexes

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Abstract : New organotin(IV) complexes containing mixed ligand Schiff bases of the type, $[(\text{nbts})\text{Bu}_3^n\text{Sn}(\text{L})]$ [where L = Cl (1), *p*-nitrophenol (2) and *o*-aminophenol (3) and (nbts) = 3-nitrobenzylidene thiosemicarbazide] and $[(\text{sb})\text{Bu}_3^n\text{Sn}(\text{L}')]]$ [where L' = 2-pic, 3-pic, isoqui (neutral nitrogenous ligands); sbH = snabH (4-6) (salicylidene-3-nitro-1-aminobenzene) and *p*-smabH (7-9) (salicylidene-4-methyl-1-aminobenzene)] have been prepared by simple metathetic reactions in C_6H_6 -MeOH mixture and characterized by elemental analysis and IR, ^1H , ^{13}C , ^{119}Sn NMR and FAB-MS spectral studies.

Keywords : Tri-*n*-butyl tin(IV) chloride, Schiff base complex, FAB-MS, IR, multinuclear NMR studies.

Introduction

Schiff bases containing 'N', 'S' and 'O' donor atoms are a class of important compounds in medicinal and pharmaceutical field. They show biological activities including antibacterial¹⁻³, antifungal⁴, anticancer⁵ and herbicidal⁶ activities. Schiff bases are utilized as starting materials in the synthesis of industrial⁶⁻⁸ and biological compound⁹⁻¹³. It is also known that chelation of metal ions with these organic ligands acts synergistically to increase their biological activities¹⁴.

During recent past, considerable progress has been made in the synthesis and characterization of organotin(IV) complexes¹⁵⁻²⁰. Biologically active organotin(IV) complexes containing various Schiff bases exhibit a broad spectrum of biological activity, which includes bactericidal²³, fungicidal²⁴ and acaricides²⁵.

Several organotin compounds exhibit promising *in vitro* antitumour activities^{21,22} against human tumour cell lines. Tin has large number of organometallic derivatives having wide range of agricultural and industrial applications. Organotin(IV) complexes with Schiff bases containing nitrogen, oxygen and sulphur donor atoms have received attention during recent years in our research laboratories^{15,23,24} too. Despite extensive work on tin(II) and tin(IV) complexes with Schiff bases there is scope for further studies on the synthetic and structural aspects of such novel complexes. This work dealt with the synthesis of

tri-*n*-butyl tin(IV) complexes containing various 'N', 'S' and 'O' donor heterocyclic ligands. The resulting complexes were studied by elemental analysis and IR, ^1H , ^{13}C , ^{119}Sn NMR and FAB-MS spectroscopy.

Results and discussion

Schiff base complexes of the type $[(\text{sb})\text{Bu}_3^n\text{Sn}(\text{L})]$ have been synthesized by the reaction of tri-*n*-butyl tin(IV) chloride with sodium salts of monodentate ligand followed by the addition of Schiff base in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio, which can be represented by the following chemical equation :

(where sb = nbts; L = *p*-nph and *o*-aph)

whereas Schiff base complexes of the type $[(\text{sb})\text{Bu}_3^n\text{Sn}(\text{L}')]]$ have been synthesized by the reaction of tri-*n*-butyl tin(IV) chloride with methanolic solution of sodium salts of Schiff base followed by the addition of neutral nitrogenous bases in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio, which can be shown as follows :

(where sbH = snabH (4-6) and *p*-smabH (7-9); L' = 2-pic, 3-pic and isoqui)

Infrared spectra :

The characteristic IR frequencies (Table 2) in the complexes (1-9) observed after complexation of ligands to metal. The ligand band appeared at 1367-1354 cm⁻¹, assigned for C=S stretching frequency of thiosemicarbazide, is blue shifted by 67-55 cm⁻¹ in the com-

plexes (1-3) indicating the coordination through sulphur atom of C=S group²⁷. Whereas the pyridine ring vibrations observed in the complexes (4-9) suggest the coordination of pyridine nitrogen to tin atom²⁸. The IR spectra of above complexes (4-9) showed the absence of band in the 3485-3350 cm⁻¹ region suggesting thereby the deprotonation of phenolic OH on complexation. Schiff bases showed the absorption bands in the region 1638-

Table 1. Synthetic, physical and analytical data^a of tri-n-butyl tin(IV) complexes

Sl. no.	Reactants (g, mmol)	Products (g, % yield)	Physical state	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)
1.	Bu ₃ ⁿ SnCl + nbts (0.41, 1.26) (0.283, 1.26)	[(nbts)Bu ₃ ⁿ SnCl] ^b 1 (0.506, 73)	Orange viscous liquid	Sn 21.46 (21.59)
2.	Bu ₃ ⁿ SnCl + nbts + Na(<i>p</i> -nph) (0.436, 1.34) (0.30 1, 1.34) (0.216, 1.34)	[(nbts)Bu ₃ Sn(<i>p</i> -nph)] 2 (0.574, 68)	Light orange viscous liquid	18.77 (18.83)
3.	Bu ₃ ⁿ SnCl + nbts + Na(<i>o</i> -aph) (0.384, 1.18) (0.265, 1.18) (0.155, 1.18)	[(nbts)Bu ₃ ⁿ Sn(<i>o</i> -aph)] 3 (0.503, 71)	Brown viscous liquid	19.81 (19.77)
4.	Bu ₃ ⁿ SnCl + 2-pic + Na(snab) (0.352, 1.08) (0.101, 1.08) (0.285, 1.08)	[(snab)Bu ₃ ⁿ Sn(2-pic)] 4 (0.506, 75)	Orange viscous liquid	18.94 (19.01)
5.	Bu ₃ ⁿ SnCl + 3-pic + Na(snab) (0.371, 1.14) (0.106, 1.14) (0.301, 1.14)	[(snab)Bu ₃ ⁿ Sn(3-pic)] 5 (0.512, 72)	Orange viscous liquid	18.95 (19.01)
6.	Bu ₃ ⁿ SnCl + isoqui + Na(snab) (0.361, 1.11) (0.143, 1.11) (0.293, 1.11)	[(snab)Bu ₃ ⁿ Sn(isoqui)] 6 (0.498, 68)	Orange viscous liquid	17.85 (17.97)
7.	Bu ₃ ⁿ SnCl + 2-pic + Na(<i>p</i> -smab) (0.397, 1.22) (0.144, 1.22) (0.285, 1.22)	[(<i>p</i> -smab)Bu ₃ ⁿ Sn(2-pic)] 7 (0.536, 74)	Yellow viscous liquid	19.85 (20.00)
8.	Bu ₃ ⁿ SnCl + 3-pic + Na(<i>p</i> -smab) (0.426, 1.31) (0.122, 1.31) (0.306, 1.31)	[(<i>p</i> -smab)Bu ₃ ⁿ Sn(3-pic)] 8 (0.598, 77)	Yellow viscous liquid	19.92 (20.00)
9.	Bu ₃ ⁿ SnCl + isoqui + Na(<i>p</i> -smab) (0.433, 1.33) (0.172, 1.33) (0.310, 1.33)	[(<i>p</i> -smab)Bu ₃ ⁿ Sn(isoqui)] 9 (0.687, 82)	Orange viscous liquid	17.85 (17.97)

^aAll compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis. ^b %Cl Found (Calcd.) : 6.41 (6.46).

Table 2. IR spectral data (cm⁻¹) of tri-n-butyl tin(IV) complexes

Complexes	ν _{Sn-C}	ν _{Sn-N}	ν _{Sn-O}	ν _{Sn-S}	ν _{C-O}	ν _{C-N}	ν _{C=S}	ν _{NO₂(asy)}	ν _{NO₂(sy)}	ν _{NH₂}
[(nbts)Bu ₃ Sn(Cl)] ^a 1	697	471	549	441	1283	1611	1309	1420(as)	1376(sy)	3455
[(nbts)Bu ₃ Sn(<i>p</i> -nph)] 2	711	469	542	408	1278	1600	1312	1412	1359	3423
[(nbts)Bu ₃ Sn(<i>o</i> -aph)] 3	720	457	553	385	1292	1593	1295	1382	1328	3370
[(snab)Bu ₃ Sn(2-pic)] 4	719	469	547	-	1278	1588	-	1409(as)	1326(sy)	-
[(snab)Bu ₃ Sn(3-pic)] 5	724	478	542	-	1293	1602	-	1411(as)	1358(sy)	-
[(snab)Bu ₃ Sn(isoqui)] 6	703	458	538	-	1284	1609	-	1407(as)	1329(sy)	-
[(<i>p</i> -smab)Bu ₃ Sn(2-pic)] 7	712	477	548	-	1283	1611	-	-	-	-
[(<i>p</i> -smab)Bu ₃ Sn(3-pic)] 8	725	465	553	-	1287	1608	-	-	-	-
[(<i>p</i> -smab)Bu ₃ Sn(isoqui)] 9	731	449	559	-	1293	1599	-	-	-	-

^aν_{Sn-Cl} observed at 289 cm⁻¹.

Table 3. NMR (^1H and ^{13}C) data (δ , ppm) of tri-*n*-butyl tin(IV) complexes

Complexes	^1H NMR (δ , ppm)			^{13}C NMR (δ , ppm)											
	HC=N	Aromatic protons		NH	NH ₂	n-Butyl protons		Aromatic carbons				n-Butyl carbons			
		CH ₂	CH ₃			C=N	C-O (phenolic)	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	
[bis]Bu ₃ ⁿ Sn(Cl)] ^a 1	9.18	6.97-6.11	0.11	2.34	1.32	0.72	157.08	158.80	141.76	126.00	121.99	28.40	28.23	26.31	13.34
[(nbis)Bu ₃ ⁿ Sn(<i>p</i> -nph)] ^a 2	8.90	7.12-6.88	0.15	2.58	1.10	0.69	156.93	159.41	141.19	125.86	122.89	28.35	27.60	26.50	13.49
[(snab)Bu ₃ ⁿ Sn(usoqui)] 6	9.23	7.05-6.57	-	-	0.90	0.61	153.77	159.49	142.09	125.50	123.00	28.21	27.53	26.20	13.25
[<i>p</i> -snab]Bu ₃ ⁿ Sn(2-pic)] 7	9.32	7.11-6.91	-	-	1.35	0.65	156.43	158.82	141.11	124.99	122.53	27.69	27.60	26.22	13.11

^aC-NH at δ 167.87 for complex **1** and 167.65 for complex **2**.

1612 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{C=N} bands which get shifted to lower frequency region in the complexes and observed at 1615–1585 cm⁻¹ indicating coordination via azomethine group²⁹. The presence of characteristic ν_{C-O} (phenolic) bands in 1299–1276 cm⁻¹ region confirm the bonding of ligands (*p*-smabH and snabH) to tin (4-9) through phenolic oxygen³⁰. The complexes displayed sharp band in the range 559–533, 483–449 and 738–694 cm⁻¹ attributed to ν_{Sn-O}, ν_{Sn-N} and ν_{Sn-C} modes³¹ respectively, whereas new band in the region 382–413 cm⁻¹ has been assigned to Sn-S stretching vibrations³².

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR spectra (Table 3) of the complexes with those of free ligands further suggest the formation of complexes. Spectra of the complexes do not display any signal in the region δ 9.4–8.6 ppm because of deshielding on complex formation, suggesting coordination through azomethine nitrogen. Signals due to protons adjacent to pyridine (ring) nitrogen observed in the region δ 9.26–8.60 ppm, suggest the involvement of ring nitrogen in bonding with organotin. The chemical shift reported for the aromatic hydrogens in the region δ 7.11–6.11 ppm have been observed to resonate at lower field in the complexes³³. The ¹H NMR spectra of all complexes exhibited characteristic signals due to *n*-butyl protons attached with tin atom. The *n*-butyl group appeared a well defined triplet at about δ 0.66 ppm and a broad multiplet in the region δ 1.35–0.90 ppm owing to the terminal CH₃ of the

long alkyl chain and the (-CH₂)₃ chain, respectively.

¹³C NMR spectra :

The formation of complexes discussed so far has been further supported by the ¹³C NMR spectra³⁴ (Table 3). The signals appeared in the range δ 159.49–158.80 ppm suggest the bonding of phenolic oxygen via metal-oxygen bond formation in Schiff base complexes. The signals observed in the region δ 28.4–27.7 ppm and δ 13.5–13.1 ppm due to resonance of carbons of (-CH₂)₃ chain and terminal CH₃ group of the long alkyl (*n*-butyl) chain, respectively.

¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra :

The δ values of the ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectra are mainly influenced by the electronegativity of the donor atoms and by the change in the coordination number of tin. Actually, an important property of the ¹¹⁹Sn chemical shift is that an increase in the coordination number of the tin atom from four to five, six or seven usually produces a large upfield shift δ (¹¹⁹Sn)³⁵. In most of the triorganotin(IV) complexes chemical shift values reported in the range of +200 to -60, -90 to -190, -210 to -400 and -440 to -560 ppm, the coordination numbers of the tin are four, five, six and seven³⁶ respectively. The complex [(nbtS)Bu₃ⁿSn(*p*-nph)] 2 studied herein, showed a broad signal at -430 ppm in ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectrum, indicating the tin atom is of hexacoordination in the complex, which has been further corroborated by FAB-MS spectral studies (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. FAB-MS fragmentation pattern of [(nbtS)Bu₃ⁿSn(*p*-nph)] (2) complex.

FAB-MS spectra :

The FAB-mass spectrum of one of the representative complex [(nbt₃)Bu₃ⁿSn(*p*-nph)] **2** showed the molecular ion peak³⁵ at *m/z* 651 corresponds to the molecular formula of the complex suggesting thereby the monomeric nature of the complex. Other important peaks observed at *m/z* 606, 590, 514, 468, 376, 349, 334, 290, 233, 176 and 119 correspond to the fragmented species (Scheme 1) after the successive removal of NO₂[•], NH₂[•], C₆H₄[•], NO₂[•], C₆H₄O[•], HCN[•], NH[•], CS[•] and C₄H₉[•] (*n*-butyl) groups respectively.

A mass spectrum (Fig. 1) of this complex, [(nbt₃)Bu₃ⁿSn(*p*-nph)] **2** was studied and fragmentation

4-methyl-1-aminobenzene and 3-nitro-1-aminobenzene respectively, whereas neutral nitrogenous ligands, such as, 2-picoline, 3-picoline and isoquinoline were used as such. Tin was estimated gravimetrically as tin oxide (SnO₂). Elemental analysis was carried out by RSIC, CDRI, Lucknow. IR spectra were recorded as nujol mull using Perkin-Elmer 1000 FT-IR spectrophotometer. NMR (¹H, ¹³C and ¹¹⁹Sn) spectra were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆/CDCl₃ on Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer. The FAB-mass spectrum was recorded on a Jeol SX 102/DA-6000 mass spectrometer using Argon/Xenon as the FAB gas.

*Synthesis of [(nbt₃)Bu₃ⁿSn(*p*-nph)] :*

To a mixture of tri-*n*-butyl tin(IV) chloride (0.436 g,

Fig. 1. FAB-MS spectrum of [(nbt₃)Bu₃ⁿSn(*p*-nph)] (**2**) complex.

pattern (Scheme 2) showed the composition for structural aspects as expected for hexacoordinated tin atom in the complex, exhibited by ¹¹⁹Sn NMR spectral studies for this complex.

Experimental

All experiments were carried out under anhydrous conditions. Reagents used were of AnalaR grade. Tri-*n*-butyl tin(IV) chloride was used as such without further purifications. Schiff bases were synthesized by previous established literature methods²⁶ using salicylaldehyde with

1.34 mmol) and sodium salt of *p*-nitrophenol (0.216 g, 1.34 mmol) in benzene-methanol mixture (~20 cm³) 3-nitrobenzylidene thiosemicarbazide (0.301 g, 1.34 mmol) was added with constant stirring and refluxed for ~3 h. The precipitated sodium chloride was filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated by distillation under reduced pressure to afford light orange viscous liquid [(nbt₃)Bu₃ⁿSn(*p*-nph)] **2** (0.574 g, 68%).

Similar method was adopted for the synthesis of [(nbt₃)Bu₃ⁿSn(*o*-nph)] **3**. The physical and analytical details are given in Table 1.

Scheme 2. FAB-MS fragmentation pattern of $[(nbt)_3Sn(p-nph)]$ (2) confirming composition and structural of the complex.

*Synthesis of $[(sb)Bu_3^nSn(L')]$ (where $L' = 2-pic, 3-pic$ and *isoqui*) :*

In a mixture of tri-n-butyl tin(IV) chloride (0.352 g, 1.08 mmol) and sodium salt of salicylidene-3-nitro-1-aminobenzene (snabH), in benzene-methanol mixture ($\sim 25\text{ cm}^3$), 2-picoline (0.101 g, 1.08 mmol) was added with constant stirring and refluxed for ~ 3 h. The precipitated sodium chloride was filtered off and the filtrate was concentrated/dried under reduced pressure to afford light orange viscous liquid $[(snab)Bu_3^nSn(2-pic)]$ 4 (0.506 g, 75%).

In a similar manner other complexes (5-9) were synthesized. The pertinent data are given in Table 1.

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